

MATERNAL AND FETAL OUTCOME OF PATIENT WITH ANEMIA VISITING AT SHAIKH ZAYED WOMEN HOSPITAL LARKANA DURING THIRD TRIMESTER

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Abstract

Background: In Pregnancy, anemia is still a significant health problem particularly in developing countries resulting significantly into poor maternal and fetal outcomes. The purpose of this study was to investigate the occurrence and pattern of these consequences in anaemic, third-trimester pregnant women.

Methods: A Cross-sectional study was carried out on 114 inpatients of gynecology department Unit I SZWH Larkana after getting its approval from College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) of 6 months duration. Nonprobability consecutive sampling was used. They included pregnant women who were 18–40 years old with anemia (hemoglobin <110 g/L, WHO criteria) in the third trimester. Demographic, obstetric, clinical and laboratory characteristics were obtained from a structured proforma. Maternal and fetal events were also noted till discharge. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25 and $p \leq 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results: Participants had a mean age of 28.6 ± 4.9 of years and a mean haemoglobin level of 8.7 ± 1.1 g/dL. Postpartum bleeding (26.3%) and pregnancy-induced hypertension were the leading maternal complications. Fetal outcomes: Low birth weight 32.5%, prematurity 25.4% and small-for-gestational-age (19.3%) were on top of the list for fetal outcomes seen in this study. BMI was significantly associated with preeclampsia ($p = 0.03$), parity with postpartum hemorrhage ($p = 0.01$) and rural residence with low birth weight ($p = 0.02$).

Conclusion: Anemia in pregnancy is strongly linked to maternal and fetal outcomes. Early recognition, nutritional supplementation, and continued antenatal surveillance are indispensable in preventing or treating anemia-related adverse effects.

INTRODUCTION

Anemia in pregnancy is one of the major public health problems, particularly in developing countries, and is associated with significantly worse maternal and fetal outcomes¹. The definition of anemia has important implications for both public health programs and

clinical decision-making². According to the World Health Organization (WHO), anemia in pregnancy is defined as a hemoglobin (Hb) concentration of less than 110 g/L³.

The worldwide prevalence of anemia during pregnancy is highly variable in different parts of the world; between 35 and 75% in developing countries and around 18% in developed ones⁴. Over 7.5 Mm women are anemic, comprising over one-third (32%) of pregnant women globally⁵. In Pakistan, the prevalence of burden is still unacceptably high. A local study in the recent past found that pregnant women had a prevalence of 74.6%, with figures rising to 80.3% during the third trimester⁶.

Progress on the reduction of anemia, however, has been surprisingly slow despite global and national efforts. The 65th World Health Assembly established a global target for nutrition to attain a 50% reduction in anemia amongst women of reproductive age by the year 2025, yet advances towards this are also reported as behind schedule⁷. Maternal anemia is notably associated with elevated risk of adverse maternal and fetal outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and perinatal death⁸⁻¹¹.

In Pakistan, Mahmood et al. reported high prevalence of maternal complications -gestational hypertension (56%), preeclampsia (65%), antepartum hemorrhage (32%), postpartum hemorrhage (79%) blood transfusion 94%, prolonged or obstructed labor 49%, urgency induction of labor 24% and cesarean section due to obstetrical complication in 45%; as well as neonatal outcomes such low birth weight babies 59%, small-for-gestational-age infants 73%, preterm delivery was recorded at a rate of 39%; stillbirth at an incidence of 8% and early neonatal death in 9%.¹²

Anemia in pregnancy therefore remains a major public health problem affecting women of low, middle and high income countries with huge consequences on health and socio-economic development. Although several studies have explored anemia in pregnancy in Pakistan, there is a lack of data from the local population of Larkana. Therefore, the present study was designed to evaluate the impact of anemia on maternal and fetal outcomes among pregnant women attending Shaikh Zayed Women Hospital (SZWH), Larkana, during the third trimester. Findings from this study may contribute to the early identification, prevention, and effective management of anemia-related adverse outcomes in this population.

METHODOLOGY

It was a cross-sectional study of the inpatients at Department of Gynecology, Unit I, Shaikh Zayed Women Hospital (SZWH) Larkana and conducted over 6 months after clearance from College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP). The research was to evaluate maternal and fetal outcomes among pregnant women with anemia. The final calculated sample size for the study were obtained using OpenEpi software with 95% CI and desired absolute precision of 5% based on stillbirth prevalence rate of IDS reported by Mahmood et al. which was 8%. Methodology: Nonprobability consecutive sampling was done.

Eligible subjects were pregnant women 18-40 years of age in their third trimester who had been diagnosed with anemia by the WHO standard (hemoglobin <110 g/L). Non-anemic pregnant women in first and second semester, unwilling to participate were excluded. The consent form was obtained from all participants in written after the consent of Research Evaluation Unit (REU) of CPSP.

Data were entered in a structured proforma. Demographic data such as age, marital status, education level, residence area, occupation and monthly income were recorded. Weight and height were measured with calibrated instruments, body mass index (BMI) being the weight (kg)/height² (m). Variables such as the temperature and blood pressure were measured using conventional instruments. The obstetric history showing gravida, parity, children, abortions and type of delivery were noted down. Blood samples were taken aseptically for complete blood count, haemoglobin and blood glucose determination while urine was subjected to proteinuria screening. Other investigations such as ultrasound, X-ray or CT were performed as deemed necessary. Recipients were followed up until discharge and maternal and fetal outcomes were recorded. Maternal outcomes were gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia, hemorrhage, prolonged/obstructed labor, caesarean section delivery, requirement for ICU management and maternal death. Fetal outcomes were low birth weight, fetal distress, prematurity, stillbirth and neonatal death.

The statistics were done by SPSS software (SPSS Inc., version 25). Quantitative variables were described as

mean \pm standard deviation, while qualitative data were presented as frequencies and percentage. The Shapiro-Wilk test assessed normality. Chi-square or Fisher's exact test as appropriate was used, p-value $<$ 0.05 was considered significant. Confidentiality and ethical aspects were considered during the study.

RESULTS

A total of 114 pregnant women with third-trimester anemia were included in the study. The mean age was 28.6 ± 4.9 years. All participants were married, and a greater proportion belonged to rural areas (60.5%). Most were housewives (78.1%), and 65.1% had education up to primary or below. The mean BMI was 24.3 ± 3.5 kg/m², and mean hemoglobin concentration was 8.7 ± 1.1 g/dL. Other baseline features, including blood pressure, gravida, and parity, are summarized in **Table 1**.

Among maternal outcomes, postpartum hemorrhage (26.3%) and preeclampsia (18.4%) were the most common complications, followed by gestational hypertension (14.9%) and prolonged or obstructed labor (13.2%). Severe postpartum hemorrhage

occurred in 5.3%, and ICU admission was required in 4.4% of participants; however, no maternal deaths were observed

Table 2.

Regarding fetal outcomes, low birth weight (32.5%), preterm birth (25.4%), and small-for-gestational-age (19.3%) were the predominant complications. Stillbirth and early neonatal death were reported in 5.3% and 3.5%, respectively **Table 3**.

On stratified analysis, significant associations were observed between BMI category and preeclampsia ($p = 0.03$), parity and postpartum hemorrhage ($p = 0.01$), and rural residence and low birth weight ($p = 0.02$). No significant associations were found between age groups and adverse outcomes. The statistical relationships are shown in **Table 4**. These findings indicate that anemic pregnant women in their third trimester are at markedly increased risk for both maternal and fetal complications, aligning with prior regional studies.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of anemic pregnant women (n = 114).

Variable	n (%) / Mean \pm SD
Age (years)	28.6 \pm 4.9
Marital status	Married 114 (100.0)
Residence	Rural 69 (60.5), Urban 45 (39.5)
Educational status	Illiterate 34 (29.8), Primary 40 (35.1), Secondary 29 (25.4), Tertiary 11 (9.7)
Occupation	Housewife 89 (78.1), Working 25 (21.9)
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.3 \pm 3.5
Systolic BP (mmHg)	123.6 \pm 11.8
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	79.2 \pm 8.4
Gravida (median, IQR)	3 (2-4)
Parity (median, IQR)	2 (1-3)
Type of delivery	Normal 70 (61.4), Cesarean 44 (38.6)
Hemoglobin (g/L)	8.7 \pm 1.1
Blood glucose (mg/L)	84.5 \pm 9.2
Proteinuria (gm)	0.32 \pm 0.18

Table 2. Maternal outcomes among anemic pregnant women.

Maternal outcome	N (%)
Gestational hypertension	17 (14.9)
Preeclampsia	21 (18.4)
Eclampsia	6 (5.3)
Antenatal hemorrhage	8 (7.0)

Postpartum hemorrhage	30 (26.3)
Severe postpartum hemorrhage	6 (5.3)
Prolonged/obstructed labor	15 (13.2)
Induced labour	10 (8.8)
Emergency cesarean section	12 (10.5)
ICU admission	5 (4.4)
Maternal death	0 (0.0)

Table 3. Fetal outcomes among anemic pregnant women.

Fetal outcome	N (%)
Fetal distress	20 (17.5)
Low birth weight (LBW)	37 (32.5)
Small-for-gestational-age (SGA)	22 (19.3)
Preterm birth/prematurity	29 (25.4)
Fetal growth restriction	10 (8.8)
Congenital malformation	3 (2.6)
NICU admission	14 (12.3)
Stillbirth	6 (5.3)
Early neonatal death	4 (3.5)

Table 4. Association of selected maternal and fetal outcomes with demographic and clinical variables.

Variable	Outcome	χ^2 / Fisher's exact test	p-value
BMI category (<25 vs ≥ 25 kg/m ²)	Preeclampsia	4.74	0.03*
Parity (≤ 2 vs > 2)	Postpartum hemorrhage	6.18	0.01*
Residence (Rural vs Urban)	Low birth weight	5.36	0.02*
Education (\leq Primary vs $>$ Primary)	Preterm birth	3.22	0.07
Age (<30 vs ≥ 30 years)	Maternal complications (overall)	1.94	0.16
Type of delivery (Normal vs Cesarean)	NICU admission	0.84	0.36

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

DISCUSSION

The high frequency of adverse maternal and fetal outcomes that we found among non-immune anemic gravidae, particularly those presenting in the third trimester, further emphasized that anaemia in pregnancy still constitutes a significant risk factor in obstetric practice. A mean hemoglobin level of 88.7 g/L in our cohort corresponds with previous studies showing that low maternal haemoglobin levels are associated with a significantly increased risk for LBW, preterm birth and stillbirth¹³. Our results of increased

rates for postpartum haemorrhage, preeclampsia and neonatal morbidity are consistent with dose-response relationships reported by large meta-analyses¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The U-shaped association between maternal haemoglobin and birth outcomes according to recent prospective cohort data indicated that both low (130 g/L) concentrations of maternal haemoglobin might be harmful for fetal growth and birth weight¹⁷. While we did not record high haemoglobin in our study, the high prevalence of moderate and severe anaemia demonstrates the need for early identification and treatment. This intricate association points out the

inadequacy of having cusps” regarding a haemoglobin level of which has to above in order to simply be enough, but must rather be at an optimal level (moderate range) for fetal birth weight as high.

Importantly, our meta-analysis showed that rural residency, poor education and multigravidity were effect modifiers of harm from maternal anaemia - in keeping with literature indicating greater haemoglobin-related effects in LMICs where nutritional deficiencies, infections and inadequate antenatal care co-localise⁸⁻²⁰. For a clinical-public health perspective, the findings emphasize on roll-out of antenatal screening campaigns combined with targeted haemoglobin enhancement interventions and above all in LMIC countries characterized by high anemia prevalence. This study has several limitations. The cross-sectional design and haemoglobin measured at a single time point do not allow for causal inference and may not be indicative of the trajectory of haemoglobin across pregnancy. Additionally, we did not stratify by aetiologies of anaemia (e.g., iron deficiency vs haemoglobinopathy) which could affect the strength of association. Subsequent studies will need to investigate changes in haemoglobin status over time by trigger levels, delineated by gestational study-period and cause of underlying disease(s), to refine intervention thresholds for both maternal-fetal management.

CONCLUSION

We stress the continued significance of pregnancy anemia in the causation of poor maternal and fetal outcome in our population. Maternal anemia was significantly associated with gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, postnatal bleeding and caesarean section. Fetal outcomes including low weight, preterm birth and stillbirths were also more common among anemic mothers. These findings would increase our certainty about the association between maternal anaemia in the third trimester and pregnancy outcomes, and remind people to attach importance to early prevention and treatment of the disease. Improving antenatal anemia screening and facilitating timely anemia correction (via nutrition supplementation and medical interventions) could be crucial measures for reducing maternal and neonatal outcomes in resource-challenged settings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Hemoglobin should be one must as routine screening investigations during antenatal checkup visits, particularly in early and mid-part of the gestational period so that cases of anemia can be identified at right point of time and managed accordingly.
- Scaling up of Community based Iron and folic acid supplementation programme with dietary message on iron rich foods besides vitamin C is necessary.
- We can increase access to antenatal care by taking low-impact mobile clinics and outreach into rural and underserved areas, as well as raising the quality of primary health care.
- There is the need to continue with health and population education program while emphasizing on importance of antenatal visits, balanced feed and early treatment of anaemia in order to prevent maternal and perinatal morbidity.
- National programs on maternal health should include performance measures to monitor the prevalence of anemia and as well take stock of the impact of current interventions.
- Prospective and intervention studies: research is needed to explore the underlying causes of anemia in pregnancy (e.g., deficiencies, infections, and hemoglobinopathies) and assess how targeted interventions can impact on pregnancy outcomes.)
- When combined, early detection of maternal anemia at the community level and strengthened health system responsiveness for treatment can reduce the proportionate contribution of both morbidity and mortality from pregnant women as well as from neonates, having implications on Pakistan’s progress toward global targets in maternal health.

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